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HIGHER EDUCATION IN ENGINEERING – A FRAGMENTED PUZZLE OF BITS AND PIECES?

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ABSTRACT

The author experiences big differences in the engineering students' ability to connect basic principles learnt in earlier courses with new concepts in a course on analogue electronics where the basic principles are the fundamentals to master the new knowledge, i.e. Ohm's law and Kirchoff's current and voltage law. Simple mathematical consequences such as dimension analysis and the meaning of the equal sign is ignored or simply not in their mind, and a reflection on the plausibility of the answer is seldom there. The students' seems to easily fall into a standard solution they remember and lack the ability to understand what actually the problem to solve is. From a survey including eleven 2nd and 3rd year students, in the span of failed exam several times to top students, it is clear that this is not only a problem for the students struggle to pass, but also from the higher performing students there are misconceptions on basic principles. This paper discusses issues on understanding and gained knowledge in the field of electrical circuits and electronics from a mathematical and conceptual view, their previous gained knowledge and the students' perception on how to study. The data comes from a test of exam questions with "check-up questions" on basic principles, a short survey on study pattern and selected interviews with five of the students from their performance on the test and/or their answers on the survey. The author suggests a model on how to highlight a new study pattern from basic principles and their future professional role.

1 INTRODUCTION

Since the 60's the focus on more student-centered teaching methods with the aim to activate students way of learning has started to develop in higher education. Until then almost all teaching consisted of lectures. Even though storytelling is a powerful tool for learning, there are several methods that are at least equally as good for learning and have the benefits of engaging and motivating students to a larger extent; far from all enjoy storytelling as the best way to learn. The problem that now occurs is that regardless of methods chosen, the teachers act independently dependent on his or hers choice of planning, execution format and learning forum. Therefore, a program that consists of many courses often suffers from a lack of coherence between the chosen teaching methods and lack of communication between teachers on the program (since they are many and work independently, almost always unaware of each other). There are institutions started in the last 50 years, for example Aalborg University, that have committed to a fixed planning and teaching methodology, but they are more of an exception that confirms the rule.

For some problems you learn a method to come up with a solution, like following a recipe. These methods works perfectly for standardised problems where you reach the same goal through repetition. It can be a procedure on how to start up an arrangement, solve a quadratic equation on the form $ax^2 + bx + c = 0$ or simply cook grandma's famous stew. The expected result is well known and even if it can be tricky to learn the correct routine for the final outcome, the procedure becomes a standard and you can repeat it nearly without conscious thinking after some iteration. Therefore, you move the thinking process from the conscious mind to the unconscious, like riding a bike; once you have learnt it you can do it for the rest of your life, as long as your physical status allows it. Another example on unconscious knowledge is learn how to play a music instrument: even though you give it up for a couple of years, you can still play it once you decide to try again. You got it in your bones.

In mathematic based studies, depending on the individual, the ability to learn standardised solutions disappears sooner or later. For some the correct handling of a common-emitter (CE) step with a transistor or the solution of an ordinary differential equation up to a certain order is possible in the same way. Learning mathematic models in a professional view has no meaning unless you are a mathematician. The applications can get into your bones, but all who have studied electrical engineering know that just learn how to calculate a standard CE step is not by far enough to understand the complexity and function of a transistor as an amplifier from a random chosen electrical scheme. For a student in an engineering program it sooner or later becomes necessary to learn more than just standardized solutions on all the problems at hand to pass the courses and get the necessary understanding of the field. The models are simply not good enough to cover all situations you are supposed to know and learn, you need to learn by experience and from a more conceptual view to understand how it works in real life. If every engineering student had a genuine

interest in their special subject, and gains knowledge from pure interest, it would be much more easy to educate them, but that is far from the reality.

Sooner or later an engineering student's knowledge has to reach a more conceptual level to learn and cope with the details. In electronics unwanted leaking current will appear, electrical fields from circuits, unknown capacitances, noise, current density in conductors etc... These are components that rarely is a factor in the laboratory work, at least not in the fundamental courses, and are often neglected in the models we use. We focus on proving the models that are the basics for the principles of electronics because we cannot explain all the factors that occur when we explore outside the arranged environments that follows the simplified models. The complexity in just learning how to use components like the OP and the transistor in the simplest of circuits are high enough to confuse the brightest of students when they lack experience. The transistor, for example, works its magic because it does not follow Ohm's law. Still they must learn how to apply Ohm's and Kirchoff's laws to calculate the properties and behaviour of the circuits.

The author have experienced surprisingly low understanding of basic principles of electrical circuits such as Ohm's (1) and Kirchoff's laws (2) on an Electrical engineering program during a course in Analogue electronics for the second year. The course introduce two new components, the operational amplifier (OP) and the transistor, and a fundamental part of getting the knowledge is about using (1) and (2) to understand the function of the components. Despite focusing on how to present the concept of the new components, many students struggle to pass the course. From experience I have spotted three main paths of learning students trust in

1. Memorise solutions on all problems that is presented on lectures, in the textbook and from old exams.
2. Decide on and learn formulas for the different assignments and problems that are presented during the course.
3. Work out and learn by heart the standard methods used for the basic OP and transistor circuits presented in the course by solving a large number of problems.

The third option is done in many different ways: Ideally they solve the problems together in a study group and discuss their solutions. Unfortunately there are often solutions on each of the textbook problems available and some students take a shortcut here and do not struggle enough to reach the necessary understanding of the suggested solution. It becomes even worse when they try to solve it and after a short while consults the solution and then move on.

2 RESEARCH QUESTION

As seen further down, there is research on the complexity of learning electronics and electrics, but the author see a void for a more holistic investigation on why the engineering students seemingly fail in understanding and apply basic concepts in electronics during their study period. It is easy to investigate difficulties in the more advanced application of transistor circuits and filters, to give a few examples.

Therefore, this inquiry is a initial survey that tries to pinpoint a reasonable explanation and a further research agenda on how the concepts can be more intuitive for the students when the electronics includes active circuits and further applications. For the study I aim to answer what are the actual thresholds the students experience and what conclusions can be drawn from their own opinion on how they learn and study.

3 METHODOLOGY

This inquiry is based on

- a quantitative comparison of the results from a test;
- the students own conception on how they study and learn; and
- five interviews with selected students,

a mixed methods approach is preferred [1]. The collected data covers both students' own view on study and learning as well as their results from the test, which gives the survey a narrative view from experience [2] complemented by the results from the test.

The students took a test with four exam questions (EQ) and additional questions for each EQ on basic circuit theory they ought to know from previous courses. They also had the opportunity to comment their solutions if they wanted. They described their way of learning and studying from proposed alternatives presented further down:

From the eleven students five were selected for a short interview based on their performance and opinion on how they study.

Therefore, the data collected consists of their solutions on their EQ and questions from previous courses, their opinion on how they study/learn the best, and the interviews.

4 LEARNING IN (ELECTRICAL) ENGINEERING

To promote deep learning and understanding in mathematics based subjects it is not the presence of a teacher that is the most important, but rather how to nurture the process amongst the students and increase their motivation and drive to reach the learning goals of the course [3]. The process of learning comes from an extensive knowledge on how to relate all the new content to a proper context, and also how it can, may or shall be used for further learning and knowledge [4, p. 192]. Learning electricity-related concepts is often confusing for various levels of learners [5] [6]. The difficulty in learning electricity, electronics, and electromagnetism concepts is attributed to their abstract nature, complexity, and microscopic features [7]. Some studies show that most difficulties experienced by learners of electricity-related concepts originate from certain abstract concepts that cannot be comprehended or associated with actual circuits [8]. The inability to see currents flowing through circuits in daily life and to comprehend abstract concepts leads to various misconceptions [9] related specifically to the understanding of current, voltage, and power consumption [10] [11] [12] [13]. Moreover, it is difficult to avoid these misconceptions through general instruction [8] [14] [15] [16]. Students do not seem

to fully understand what a "signal" physically is. They also lack a functional understanding of a frequency-based representation of a filter [17]. From [4, p. 190f] we have that the classroom and the teacher is different from the everyday meaning of a room inside four walls and a person in that room guiding a group of learners: Teaching starts the day you decide to setup a program, and the learning environment shall be designed from how it best suits the study groups.

When we as novices approach new knowledge we rely on our experience and previous knowledge. From this standpoint we develop an approach based on our intuition and interpretation of the problems we are facing, our intuitive knowledge. From [18] we have that intuitive knowledge is making sense of intellectual awareness. The most obvious problem with intuitive knowledge is when the intuition is wrong, i.e. from the basic principles it is hard to generalize an intuition that holds. Therefore, it is utmost important for the teacher to provide the students with tools (read learning environments) where they can better their intuition for the concept. For electronics it is complicated since you cannot directly observe what happens, only consequences of the action. Together this calls for a larger possibility for misconceptions in electronics and we cannot simply rely on intuitive knowledge as an ingredient in the process; all concepts need to be explained and interpreted for each student.

5 RESULTS

5.1 The test

The students took the test three and a half months after the regular exam where the five reference persons got their passing grades, one passed (3), two of them passed with credit (4) and the other two passed with distinction (5). The other six had another opportunity two months later where three of them participated and failed. Two of the failed students are from the previous year. They are allowed to bring a calculator, the textbook, all their own notes produced during the course and a formula handbook of their own choice on the exam. The students were told that it would count as an ordinary exam if they passed. In the test there were two control questions from their previous courses on a basic level, see below.

Question 1 is a typical passive lowpass filter where they shall present the frequency response with a Bode plot. *Extra question:* Calculate the current through the capacitor (Simple Ohm's law).

Question 2 is a basic CS amplifier (FET type of transistor). The correct calculated A_v was given and task was from a given U_{in} calculate the signal current through R_D where the output signal lies. All the signal parameters for the chosen transistor is presented, although they are not needed for the solution of the problem. So instead of the normal procedure to determine the amplification they shall calculate a signal current from a given input signal. *Extra question:* Calculate the dc current in one of the resistors connected to the Gate (A simple case of Kirchoff II and Ohm's law).

Question 3 is a simple quiescent point calculation for a bjt where the only “trick” is that it is a CB amplifier, which has the same setup as the basic CE amplifier when deciding the quiescent point.

Question 4 is a basic AC OP amplifier circuit (inverted) where the drawing circuit is not in a standard format, but not complicated, just drawn with a different layout than they normally see them. They shall calculate the amplification $A_V(\omega) = \frac{U_{out}}{U_{in}}$ when $\omega \rightarrow \infty$ and $\omega \rightarrow 0$

There are lots of data that can be interpreted from their solutions, but the focus in this study is: Do they understand what to do, and Do they know how to solve the problem, and What are the typical errors?

Q1: All students start with setting up the general criteria for the transfer function. Seven of them present a correct transfer function, two of the higher graded students get lost in the algebra and therefore not reaching a correct transfer function on Bode’s normal form. Three of the not passed students make calculation errors and get unreasonable answers without commenting them (for example $I_C=10,8kA$). Further from the not passed students the equal sign is incorrect used repeatedly. The passed students and one of the not passed set up Ohm’s law for the current through the capacitor.

Q2: Three passed and one not passed understand what to do. Noone of them present the correct answer clearly showing lack of understanding of what voltage difference is. The students that goes wrong starts with calculating the quiescent point although it is not needed. The passed students calculate the correct dc current and two of not passed managed that as well.

Q3: Surprisingly many (all not passed but one and one that had passed) started their calculation from the key numbers normally used when dimensioning of the amplifier is done, i.e. a totally wrong approach. The one that passed then discovered the mistake and came up with the correct answer. It is obvious from this task that the non passed students have flaws in how to apply Ohm’s and Kirchoff’s laws.

Q4: Since the question is a standard setup for an inverting amplifier most of them were able to get the right expression for the relationship between the input signal and the output. Four of the students did not deliver a solution but three of them claimed lack of time as the reason, which made sense. One forgot the minus sign and a couple did not answer the question which was how the amplifier acts for the extreme values zero and infinity and presented their answer in a Bode plot.

In general: Students that have not passed make calculation errors or simply use the wrong method and get in many cases unreasonable answers without commenting on the reasonability. Structure, i.e. using the equal sign and analyse and use the dimensions right are common mistakes; more than once voltages were expressed as impedance. The ability to evaluate their answers are surprisingly low. Even passed students can answer with unreasonable numbers, but the real misconceptions were

among the non passed ones: it is a big difference between 1,5A and 10kA, even though both are not possible after a simple consideration on voltage drop.

5.2 Their view of learning and studying

They got a number of propositions on how to study to choose from, see below. They were asked to determine what category represented them best, or formulate it in their own words.

- “By heart”: Memorise solutions on all the problems from the lectures and the textbook
- “Formulas”: Determine and learn formulas for the problems that are central for the course
- “Methods”: Abrasion of the standardized methods for the basic circuits from the course by solving a great number of problems
- “Planning”: Follow the course planning that the teacher presents to the letter.
- “Examstudy”: I study old exams and learn the solutions of the problems

Table 1 - students opinion on learning and study pattern

Student #	Description	By heart	Formulas	Methods	Planning	Examstudy
1	Not passed	Works	through	all the	material	
2	Not passed	-	1	3	4	1
3	Grade 3	5	2	1	3	4
4	Not passed	4	2	1	5	3
5	Grade 5	2	5	1	4	3
6	Grade 4	4	3	1	2	5
7	Grade 4	-	2	3	1	4
8	Grade 5	4	5	1	2	3
9	Not passed	-	1	2	-	-
10	Not passed	1	1	-	-	-
11	Not passed	2	4	3	5	1

As seen most of the students used more than one alternative, many of them used all the alternatives. The three students that have failed miserably a number of times have "Formulas" and "Examstudy" as their first choice. One who passed with distinction, student #5, failed the test and he puts a "4" in "Planning", while the other "high graders" prioritise the "Planning".

5.3 The interviews

Student #3, #4, #8, #9 and #10 was selected for interviews. The interviews were with open ended questions on how they experience the course and their gained knowledge and the result from the test.

#3 (Grade 3): The discussion quickly focused on whether solutions on problems are helpful or an obstacle for the students. His view and standpoint was that having solutions available is beneficial in the cases where you get stuck and the group cannot understand why they go wrong. His conclusion was that solutions on problems are beneficial as long as they are discussed within the study group until they reach a proper understanding and not just accept that there is a solution.

#4 (Not passed): This student performed very well on the test and described his study pattern that he first strive for a theoretical and fact based foundation from the start. Then he starts to solve a lot of problems to pinpoint where he has gaps of knowledge and returns to the textbook and lecture notes to fill the gaps.

#8 (Grade 5): He simply study after the planning and try to reach a proper understanding of all the methods presented in the course. He has great success so far in

his studies. Though not worked with electronics before, he has a parallel project for a private matter he works on.

#9 (Not passed): This is a student from a year before that have failed the exam five times, and did so this time as well. He writes everything down from each session with the teacher and claims that he solves every suggested problem in the textbook. From the interview it became clear that he has huge gaps in understanding the basics for electrical circuits and often presents the proposed solution from a ready made formula, often the right one, but seldom explained or drawn from the problem at hand. It is also clear that the understanding for quantities is simply not there; whether it is a voltage or current is not relevant for the formula at hand, just the outcome.

#10 (Not passed): He cannot accept his inability and shortcoming and starts immediately talking about stress and circumstances outside his studies that has affected him. When discussing the problems from the test it is obvious he is far from having the slightest idea on what the circuits are about; all approaches either come from formulas he memorized or a direct random guess.

6 SUMMARY

Although many students work continuously and in groups during the course, there are gaps in fundamentals as algebra and basic circuit theory, and getting a grasp of the content. The worse they perform, the more narrow (and therefore bigger risk for choosing wrong solution pattern) the thinking around the problem becomes, and they associate to some standard solution they remember simply from the layout of the problem. The holistic view is from relatively small to non existent.

The top-down perspective right from the start: If you are to become an electrical engineer, you need to know what are you supposed master when you have the degree and take on a position within the field. By starting with courses in general electrical and electronics theory learning Ohm's law, Kirchoff's laws of current and voltage and circuit theory, it must be in the context of your professional role. Data implies poor outcome in just learning how to calculate voltages and currents in solvable exercises. It is the same for learning how to operate the operational amplifier or the transistor. Therefore, all electronics must be seen in a bigger picture to help nurture the students' intuition on the concepts. Students already involved in practical electronics are rare from my experience. Therefore, the best you can do in the first part of a program, and following through the whole program, in electronics and/or electric is connect the content from a professional's perspective; presented as part of real life problems.

7 FURTHER WORK

A more extensive study on the course in Analogue electronics will be done included in the ordinary teaching sessions for next semester analysing all participating students from the data this study presents. The material for the course will be from a professional electrical engineer's perspective where all learning goals are motivated and presented from the real world.

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